

THE ROLE OF COUNSELLING GUIDANCE ON CYBERBULLYING BEHAVIOUR AND ITS INFLUENCE ON STUDENT RESILIENCE: A STUDY OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN YOGYAKARTA

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ABSTRACT

Bullying in the school environment is still a significant challenge for educational institutions in Indonesia, affecting students' resilience, emotional well-being, confidence, and academic engagement. Victims with low resilience often experience social withdrawal, academic difficulties, and psychological distress. This makes schools, especially counseling guidance teachers, play an important role in creating a healthy school environment. This study examines bullying behavior and its impact on the resilience of junior high school students in Yogyakarta. A descriptive qualitative method was used in this study with data collected through interviews by 140 students and 14 guidance and counseling teachers from 14 schools. The results showed that 77.1% of students had experienced bullying, which led to insecurity, anxiety, lack of confidence, frustration, isolation, and helplessness, all of which were closely linked to resilience. Additionally, cyberbullying has emerged as a growing problem, with some students reporting online harassment, negative comments, and ostracization on social media, often in conjunction with bullying at school. Cyberbullying poses a greater risk due to its persistence, anonymity, and wide audience reach, making it more difficult for victims to escape its effects. To mitigate these impacts, schools should adopt comprehensive intervention strategies, including counseling services for victims and perpetrators, anti-bullying education, Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT), the KiVa Anti-Bullying Program, and digital literacy training. Strengthening school policies, safe reporting systems, and support networks is essential to fostering student resilience, enabling them to overcome bullying experiences and thrive academically and socially.

Keywords: *Counseling Guidance, Cyberbullying, Resilience, Students, Intervention Strategies*

1. INTRODUCTION

The current phenomenon of violence in the school environment is of great concern to all groups, including educator and parents of students [1]. Behavior that does not reflect being a student is also shown through actions that lead to violence or bullying, which are often called bullying [2]. The problem of bullying in recent years has increased significantly and has a profound traumatic impact on students who experience it [3]. Bullying is an action carried out by another person to someone to hurt either physically or psychologically. [4] stated that psychological impacts are very likely to be experienced by people who have problems related to unpleasant actions. [5]. More than 30% of students in this study were identified as being involved in cyberbullying as victims or perpetrators, and one in four students (25.7%)

reported having been involved in cyberbullying as a perpetrator of bullying.

The violence that occurs will impact the psychology of students and affect the process of education or learning of students at school [6]. Bullying is a violent behavior that is often found in the school environment, both at the elementary school level and at school. The phenomenon that occurs today is that bullying does not only happen face to face but the use of technology is widely carried out by perpetrators of bullying violence, which is then known as cyberbullying. Bullying is also carried out with traditional intimidation [7], [8]. Cyberbullying and traditional bullying that are currently developing reflect the dynamics of bullying violence among students in the school environment. The side of the perpetrators of cyberbullying, namely by utilizing technology to do it against bullying victims, such as social media,

which is currently widely used. At the same time, traditional bullying is done directly to the victim. Therefore, with the phenomenon of cyberbullying and traditional bullying, many problems arise for students at school.

The emergence of this behavior can be caused by several factors that cause the perpetrator to bully the victim. The Federation of Indonesian Teachers' Unions (FSGI) has released data on bullying cases in schools in 2023. From January to September, there were 23 cases of bullying. Of the 23 cases, 50% occurred at the junior high school level, 23% at the elementary school level, 13.5% at the high school level, and 13.5% at the vocational school level. Most cases occur at the junior high school level and are carried out by fellow students or educators.

Furthermore, according to the Chairperson of the Expert Council of the Federation of Indonesian Teachers' Unions (FSGI), Retno Listyarti, her party found at least 12 cases of bullying from January to May 2023. Children are not taught to behave in a bullying manner. This behavior is also not taught directly to children. Various factors influence a child to develop into a bully. These factors include biological and temperament factors and the influence of family, friends, and the environment. Research shows that individual, social, environmental risk and protection factors determine bullying behavior. Furthermore, the Indonesian Child Protection Commission (KPAI) revealed that there were around 3,800 cases of bullying in Indonesia throughout 2023. Almost half of them occurred in educational institutions, including Islamic boarding schools.

The impact of violence that occurs in the school environment affects the psychology of students. [9] wrote that 15.8% of students reported cyberbullying, and 25.9% reported school intimidation in the last 12 months. The majority (59.7%) of cyberbullying victims were also victims of bullying at school; 36.3% of bullying victims at school were also victims of cyberbullying. In adolescence, they are very vulnerable to bullying, which will eventually lead to traumatic problems, and the majority (61.8%) of adolescents have trauma problems that they face [10]. Furthermore, [11]. Peer bullying has been largely ignored by health professionals but should be considered a significant risk factor and a severe problem.

The impact of bullying is very detrimental to the victim, including anxiety, inability to control oneself, quick experiencing negative emotions,

problems relating to family, and sleep disorders [12]. Furthermore [11] wrote that childhood bullying victims, including those who are bullied by others (bully-victims), are at increased risk of poor health. The impact of bullying violence has a very high risk for bullying victims [11]. The effect will significantly affect student behavior in interactions with others and themselves.

The psychological impact experienced by victims of bullying makes it important for us to explore protective factors that can reduce its impact. The psychological impact that victims experience the most is social anxiety. [13] explained in their research that victims of bullying can significantly increase social anxiety in children. This social anxiety can interfere with a child's ability to interact with others, build relationships, and feel safe in a social environment. This makes it important for us to give our children internal strength that can help them overcome these difficulties. Resilience is one of the protective factors that has a role in allowing a person to recover from bullying. Resilience refers to the ability to adapt positively despite experiencing significant stress and trauma. Research [14] conceptualizes resilience as a psychological defense mechanism that can help victims survive and grow in the face of their difficulties. For victims of bullying, resilience plays an important role in reducing their psychological problems, rebuilding self-esteem, and improving social functioning. So that resilience has an important role as an anti-bullying strategy in the school environment.

Students who experience violence or bullying at school, either directly or traditionally bullying or through cyberbullying, will have problems that will interfere with their development tasks, especially in the behavior that appears. Therefore, students who are victims of bullying need good resilience so that they can continue to grow into developed individuals. Victims of bullying without proper handling will hurt themselves. The results of research by [15] show that victims of intimidation or bullying at school are positively related to self-harm.

Resilience is the ability to cope and adapt to complex events or problems that occur in life. Surviving stressful conditions and dealing with adversity or trauma experienced in life [16]. Furthermore, according to [17], resilience is the ability or human capacity possessed by a person, group, or community that enables them to face, prevent, minimize, and even eliminate the adverse impacts of unpleasant conditions or even change

miserable life conditions into something normal to overcome. Adolescents with low resilience tend to be weak and helpless and have difficulty dealing with difficult situations or stressful situations because they are not used to adapting to challenges [18].

Guidance and counseling teachers have an important role in fostering student resilience. Resilience is not only needed by victims but also needed by everyone. This is intended to improve the ability to overcome bullying behavior [19]. The roles and responsibilities of guidance and counseling teachers are to provide intervention and support for victims, identify cases, and provide counseling for individuals and groups [20], [21]. Thus, in-depth research is needed regarding what roles guidance and counseling teachers can play in overcoming bullying cases in schools.

2. METHOD

This study uses a mixed-method research design, combining a qualitative approach using interviews as a research instrument and a quantitative method for analysing interview results through statistical analysis.

2.1 Participants and Research Instruments

The participants in this study consisted of students and counseling teachers from 14 schools in Yogyakarta, comprising a total of 140 students and 14 BK teachers. Sampling utilising the saturation sampling method, where the entire population was utilised as samples. This study employed structured interviews implementing a predetermined list of questions for data collecting. The instrument employed in this study was an interview guide that explained the interview activities used to collect data. The interview questions offer two response options: "yes" and "no". Table 1 below displays the questions presented by the researcher to the participants.

Table 1: List of Research Interview Guide Questions

No	Question
1.	Have you ever been bullied by friends at school?
2.	Do you feel miserable when your friends bully you?
3.	When you were bullied, did you consult a guidance counselor?
4.	Has your guidance counselor ever helped you to recover as a victim of bullying?
5.	Do you feel anxious, scared, lack confidence in activities, and feel inferior when you are bullied?

The five questions above then become variables in the quantitative analysis in this study.

2.2 Data Analysis

The data obtained from the interview results were subsequently analysed using statistical methods, specifically descriptive statistics and the Chi-square test. The Chi-Square test is utilised to compare two variables measured on a nominal scale. This test can compare two or more categorised data groups. This study will evaluate numerous hypotheses, including:

H1: There is a relationship between the experience of being bullied and feelings of sadness after being bullied.

H2: There is a relationship between the experience of being bullied and psychological impacts such as anxiety, inferiority, lack of self-confidence or fear.

H3: There is a relationship between the experience of being bullied and the behavior of consulting a Guidance and Counseling teacher.

H4: There is a relationship between feelings of anxiety, fear, lack of self-confidence and inferiority with the behavior of consulting with counseling teacher.

H5: There is a relationship between consulting a guidance and counseling teacher and the success of victims recovering from the impact of bullying.

The five hypotheses were subsequently analysed utilising SPSS version 26. Decision-making relies on the P-value, which is the output that results from the SPSS program. The hypothesis will be accepted at a 5% significance level if the P-value is below this level of significance.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Descriptive Statistics

Initially, this study employs a descriptive statistical analysis of the variables that are discussed in the interview. The descriptive statistical analysis results are presented in Table 2 as follows:

Table 2: Statistic Descriptive

Question	Sum		Precent		Mean	SD
	Yes	No	Yes	No		
Have you ever been bullied by friends at school?	108	32	77.1 %	22.9 %	0.77	0.421
Do you feel miserable when your friends bully you?	91	49	65 %	35%	0.65	0.479

When you were bullied, did you consult a guidance counselor?	59	81	42.1 %	57.9 %	0.42	0.496
Has your guidance counselor ever helped you to recover as a victim of bullying?	88	52	62.9 %	37.1 %	0.63	0.485
Do you feel anxious, scared, lack confidence in activities, and feel inferior when you are bullied?	94	46	67.1 %	32.9 %	0.67	0.471
Total	140	140				

According to Table 2, a significant proportion of junior high school students in Yogyakarta, specifically 77.1% of 140 respondents, have experienced bullying. This shows that bullying among students remains widespread. Moreover, 65% of students feel sadness when faced with bullying by others, while 67.1% describe feelings of anxiety, fear, diminished confidence in activities, and a sense of inferiority as a result of bullying. This indicates that bullying behaviour in schools significantly affects the victims, necessitating effective intervention by guidance and counselling educators. [22] more than 30% of students in this study were identified as being involved in cyberbullying as victims or perpetrators, and one in four students (25.7%) reported having been involved in cyberbullying as a perpetrator of bullying.

Guidance and counseling teachers have a strategic role in helping students who experience bullying at school. The results of field research show that 58% of students who are victims of bullying do not want to consult or get assistance from guidance and counseling teachers at school. This indicates that students who are victims of bullying are reluctant to consult with guidance and counseling teachers at school for various considerations and reasons. The data also shows that 63% of students who are victims of bullying have received assistance from guidance and counseling teachers to rise from adversity so as not to become individuals who feel helpless, inferior, and depressed with the circumstances they feel

[14]. That resilience can be seen as a defense mechanism that allows people to thrive in adversity

Table 3. Identification of the behavior and impact of bullying victims in Yogyakarta City

No	Indicator	Field description/data
1	Bullying behavior	Mocking parents' names because of body odor, being ordered around, not being invited as friends, being threatened, being called a dwarf, being called a squint, being told to do push-ups, being called a sick person, being called a kid, fat, black, being hit and humiliated in public.
2	The impact of bullying	Insecure, low self-esteem in activity, anxious, uncomfortable, lack of confidence in activities, embarrassed, frustrated, angry, unwilling to socialize, afraid, feeling pressured, feeling isolated, uncomfortable in class, and feeling helpless.

The behavior and impacts listed in the table are not only carried out by a handful of students but there are indications that bullying behavior is carried out by the majority of students either directly or by using cell phones. Sending accusatory, frightening, and threatening messages is often encountered by guidance and counseling teachers. [9]. The majority of 59.7% of cyberbullying victims are also victims of bullying at school; 36.3% of bullying victims at school are also victims of cyberbullying.

The table shows that bullying behaviors encountered in schools include mocking parents' names, because of body odor, being ordered around, not being invited to be friends, threatening, being called a dwarf, being called a squint, being told to do push-ups, being called a sick person, being called a kid, fat, black, being hit and humiliated in public. The study's results Borualogo & Gumilang (2019) show that bullying in schools is relatively high and concerning. This shows that bullying behavior in schools is widespread and is carried out and felt by victims of bullying. Bullying is an action carried out by other people to someone to hurt them both physically and psychologically [23], [24]. In several incidents of bullying behavior, especially for victims, guidance and counseling teachers take action to summon the students concerned, both as perpetrators and as victims, at different times. The guidance and counseling teacher carries out the summons to the guidance and counseling teacher's room to ask for information about why the behavior was carried out

on other students. Then, when interviewed by guidance and counseling teachers, the facts show that the victims are terrified in certain situations because they feel that they are victims of bullying by their friends at school. In addition, the victims are unable to survive fighting or try to be strong when they become victims of bullying; this is characterized by only accepting and being silent when they become victims of bullying. Likewise, the impacts felt by students who are victims of bullying can be described as including Insecure, anxiety, unpleasant, not confident, embarrassed, frustration, inferior, anger, not wanting to socialize, fear, feeling depressed, feeling isolated, uncomfortable in class, and feeling helpless, [11]. The impacts will significantly affect students' behavior in interacting with others and themselves.

3.2 Chi-Square Test

The results of the Chi-Square test on the hypothesis in the study were carried out using the SPSS version 26 program as follows.

Table 4. The Result of Chi-Square Test

Hypothesis	Pearson Chi-Square	P-Value	Decision
There is a relationship between the experience of being bullied and feelings of sadness after being bullied	77.037	0.000	Accepted
There is a relationship between the experience of being bullied and psychological impacts such as anxiety, inferiority, lack of self-confidence or fear	84.767	0.000	Accepted
There is a relationship between the experience of being bullied and the behavior of consulting a Guidance and Counseling teacher.	30.215	0.000	Accepted
There is a relationship between feelings of anxiety, fear, lack of self-confidence and inferiority with the behavior of consulting with	27.480	0.000	Accepted

counseling teacher			
There is a relationship between consulting a guidance and counseling teacher and the success of victims recovering from the impact of bullying	54.884	0.000	Accepted

Based on the results in Table 4, the following conclusions can be drawn:

H1: There is a relationship between the experience of being bullied and feelings of sadness after being bullied.

Table 4 shows that the P-value of 0.000 is lower than the study's significance criterion of 0.05. As a result, the idea that bullying among students creates feelings of grief is directly felt by the tormented kids. Bullying can induce emotional distress, such as depression, low self-esteem, and thoughts of hopelessness. These mental issues can occasionally lead to thoughts of self-harm [10], [25]. Victims may feel socially inadequate and alienated, exacerbating feelings of melancholy and depression [26], [27]. Victims, on the other hand, frequently experience peer rejection and struggle to form and keep friendships, which can contribute to feelings of loneliness and melancholy [10]. Bullying has a clear impact on kids' academic performance, increasing absenteeism and decreasing concentration and interest in school activities [27].

H2: There is a relationship between the experience of being bullied and psychological impacts such as anxiety, inferiority, lack of self-confidence or fear.

Being bullied has psychological effects such as anxiety, inferiority, fear, and a lack of self-confidence. This is shown by the Chi-Square test, which gives a P-value of 0.000, less than the significance level of 0.05. Many studies have shown that victims of bullying indicate higher levels of anxiety. This is evident in both traditional and cyberbullying cases, with victims of cyberbullying expressing higher levels of anxiety. Anxiety can be caused by bullying and is influenced by aspects such as self-esteem and locus of control [26], [28]. Bullying has a substantial impact on self-esteem, resulting in feelings of low self-esteem and lack of confidence. Victims frequently report low self-esteem, which may

mediate the link between bullying and other psychological issues such as depression and anxiety. This low self-esteem can persist until adulthood, compromising general well-being [29]. Bullying, on the other hand, is unpredictable and can cause chronic anticipatory anxiety, in which victims are constantly afraid of future bullying happenings. This is especially true for people who are highly sensitive to unanticipated risks [30]. Another typical side effect of bullying is depression, which is frequently associated with anxiety. Bullying victims are more likely to have depressive symptoms, which are annoyed by low self-esteem and a lack of social support [31], [32].

H3: There is a relationship between the experience of being bullied and the behavior of consulting a Guidance and Counseling teacher.

There is a correlation between the behaviour of students who are victims of bullying and the experience of being suffering, including the requirement to consult a guidance and counselling teacher. This is shown by the Chi-Square test, which yields a P-value of 0.000, which is less than the significance level of 0.05. Bullying has a significant long-term impact on the mental health of victims, including increased levels of depression, anxiety, and low self-esteem. These mental health problems often encourage students to seek support from mental health services, including school counselors [33]. Students who perceive their teachers as supportive are less likely to experience severe bullying and are more likely to seek help. Conversely, harsh discipline from teachers can worsen bullying victimization and reduce students' desire to seek help [34].

H4: There is a relationship between feelings of anxiety, fear, lack of self-confidence and inferiority with the behavior of consulting with counseling teacher.

Table 4 indicates that hypothesis 4 has a P-value lower than its significance level. The hypothesis states a relationship among anxiety, fear, lack of self-confidence, and feelings of inferiority in relation to the behaviour of seeking consultation with a guidance counsellor. Individuals subjected to bullying often show higher levels of anxiety and depression. This emotional state can greatly influence individuals' ability and willingness to seek support [35], [36]. Due to the emotional and psychological effects of bullying, victims frequently experience social anxiety and fear, hindering their ability to seek assistance from a guidance counsellor [37]. Effective interventions,

including cognitive behavioural therapy and psychoeducation, are necessary as they have demonstrated efficacy in reducing anxiety and enhancing coping strategies, thereby increasing the likelihood of students seeking help [38]. Conversely, school-based programs are necessary to enhance social skills, offer emotional support, and cultivate a positive school environment that encourages students to seek assistance [39].

H5: There is a relationship between consulting a guidance and counseling teacher and the success of victims recovering from the impact of bullying.

Research indicates a correlation between consultations with guidance and counselling teachers and the successful recovery of victims from the effects of bullying. The Chi-Square test results in a P-value of 0.000, which is below the significance level of 0.05. Guidance counsellors serve as vital for handling bullying incidents. They perform multiple duties, such as engaging with victims and perpetrators, and frequently seek assistance from other adults [37]. Counsellors deliver individual and group counselling to victims, facilitating the resolution of psychological and social adjustment issues resulting from bullying [21]. School-based programs incorporating counselling and training effectively mitigate the effects of bullying on victims. Research indicates that cooperative-supportive intervention strategies employed by teachers and counsellors yield the greatest success in addressing bullying, both in the short and long term [40], [41]. Teacher emotional support serves as a protective factor that can substantially decrease the likelihood of suicide among bullying victims. Positive teacher-student relationships correlate with improved psychological adjustment and decreased instances of bullying victimisation [42]. Conversely, family support, alongside teacher support, is crucial in the recovery process of bullying victims [43].

Based on the results of the analysis above, it can be concluded that bullying has a major impact on students' psychology, so they need to be equipped with resilience in dealing with bullying cases. Bullying is an action carried out by other people to someone to hurt them both physically and psychologically [23], [24]. In several incidents of bullying behavior, especially for victims, guidance and counseling teachers take action to summon the students concerned, both as perpetrators and as victims, at different times. The guidance and counseling teacher carries out the summons to the

guidance and counseling teacher's room to ask for information about why the behavior was carried out on other students. Then, when interviewed by guidance and counseling teachers, the facts show that the victims are terrified in certain situations because they feel that they are victims of bullying by their friends at school. In addition, the victims are unable to survive fighting or try to be strong when they become victims of bullying; this is characterized by only accepting and being silent when they become victims of bullying. Likewise, the impacts felt by students who are victims of bullying can be described as including Insecure, anxiety, unpleasant, not confident, embarrassed, frustration, inferior, anger, not wanting to socialize, fear, feeling depressed, feeling isolated, uncomfortable in class, and feeling helpless, [11]. The impacts will significantly affect students' behavior in interacting with others and themselves.

The impact felt in the results of this study shows that it is closely related to the resilience of bullying victims. Furthermore, students who are victims of bullying need to have resilience so that they can escape the impact of bullying they experience. Pidgeon et al. (2014) define resilience as the ability to respond well to problems, succeed in the face of adversity, and have more hope in difficult situations [44]. The study results Putri Amallia (2020) showed a significant increase in resilience before and after being given individual counseling treatment with a solution-focused brief counseling approach. The results of the study revealed that students who were victims of bullying had difficulty recovering from the bullying they experienced and managing the pressures of life they received [45].

This study showed that bullying within the school environment significantly affects student resilience, particularly regarding anxiety, reduced self-confidence, and difficulties in socialization. This data correlates with Schneider et al. (2012), which indicates that bullying victims often endure psychological stress that impacts their emotional well-being. Resilience is a crucial element in helping students overcome the effects of bullying, as those with increased resilience are more adept at managing the social and psychological stress caused by bullying experiences [9].

Bullying has spread from physical interactions at school to the digital realm in the form of cyberbullying as technology has advanced. Cyberbullying is the use of communication technology, such as social media and instant messaging, to continuously threaten or harass someone [7]. Several studies have found that cyberbullying is often more dangerous than

traditional bullying since attacks can occur without limitations of space and time, and perpetrators can remain anonymous [46]. Although this study did not specifically measure the impact of cyberbullying on student resilience, interviews with several students indicated that, in addition to bullying at school, they were faced with harassment via social media in the form of negative comments, rumors, and online threats. This result matches the findings of Schneider et al. (2012), who discovered that 59.7% of cyberbullying victims also experienced bullying in school, implying a relationship between the two forms of bullying.

To reduce the effects of bullying, several methods have been developed that improve student resilience. Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) is an effective strategy that supports students in changing negative behaviors into more adaptive ones, so improving their coping mechanisms against bullying-related stress [44]. Group-based cognitive-behavioral therapy has been shown to reduce anxiety and improve students' self-confidence when dealing with bullying within school environments [47]. In addition, cognitive therapy methods, school-based anti-bullying programs like the KiVa Anti-Bullying Program have demonstrated effectiveness in reducing bullying cases while improving students' social competencies, especially through empathy-driven strategies and teacher interventions [21].

Various ways can be used to help students build resilience in the face of bullying. The Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT) approach has been demonstrated to be beneficial in helping adolescents build stronger coping skills, allowing them to better handle stress and anxiety caused by bullying [44]. Group-based cognitive-behavioral therapy has been shown to reduce anxiety and improve students' self-confidence when dealing with bullying within school environments. Situmorang & Wibowo (2018) found that group counselling using the Cognitive Behaviour Therapy (CBT) technique, combined with passive and active music therapy, effectively reduced academic anxiety among millennial age students. On the other side, group counselling services can help students become more resilient. [48] demonstrated that group counselling services are helpful at improving student resilience. In contrast [49] found that structured group counselling significantly promotes resilience, self-efficacy, and racial identification in teenagers. There is additional data that shows that biblicounseling improves student resilience. Biblicounseling is a technique that builds on bibliotherapy principles. Biblicounseling

improves the resilience of bullying victims [50]. Furthermore, school-based anti-bullying initiatives, such as the KiVa Anti-Bullying Program, have been effective in lowering bullying rates by incorporating instructors and the school environment in the development of an empathy culture. Social support from teachers, friends, and family is particularly vital in building student resilience because it gives victims a sense of security and helps them cope with the psychological effects of bullying [40].

In addition to psychological interventions and school-based programs, social support from teachers and family is crucial in helping students develop resilience. Zhang et al. (2024) found that students who felt supported by their social environment were better able to deal with the psychological effects of bullying than those who did not have a strong support system. In the context of cyberbullying, digital awareness training is an important strategy for students to improve their online interactions, learn how to report harassment, and establish healthy social media behaviors [41]. Students are expected to develop greater resilience through a combination of psychological interventions, strong school policies, and adequate social support, allowing them to not only survive bullying experiences but also grow into more resilient individuals when confronted with social challenges in the real and digital worlds.

Preventive measures against bullying behaviour are not only a concern for victims of bullying but also a concern for everyone because anyone can engage in bullying behaviour. To form an anti-bullying character in yourself and your child, you can do it in several ways as follows:

1. Increase resilience

Developing resilience can help overcome bullying and reduce its impact. Resilience training can be integrated into the school curriculum and extracurricular activities [51]. Teaching children to manage their emotional reactivity can reduce bullying behaviour and help them deal with stress more effectively [52].

2. Foster empathy and kindness

Empathy is essential in preventing bullying. Learning that teaches empathy using interactive and game-based media can effectively reduce bullying behaviour [53], [54]. Encouraging acts of kindness and integrating kindness into the school curriculum can foster a positive school climate and reduce bullying behaviour [55], [56].

3. Improve social and emotional learning

Implementing SEL programs in schools can improve social competence, encourage prosocial behaviour, and create a supportive learning environment, thereby reducing cases of bullying in schools [57], [58]. A caring and inclusive school environment can reduce bullying by encouraging respect and understanding among students [59], [60].

4. Comprehensive anti-bullying strategies

Effective anti-bullying programs involve the entire school community, including teachers, students, parents, and administrators. They address the social dynamics of bullying and promote a culture of respect [61]. Schools that focus on student strengths and promote positive behaviours rather than those that focus solely on addressing negative behaviours are more effective in preventing bullying [62].

5. Parent and community involvement

Parents play a critical role in developing resilience and empathy in children. Engaging parents in anti-bullying efforts and providing them with resources to support their children can increase the effectiveness of these programs [63]. Collaboration with community members and organizations can provide additional support and resources for anti-bullying initiatives [61].

This study discusses the attitude of bullying victims towards what happened to them. The study has also not focused on cyberbullying cases in depth. The results of the study show that not all victims of bullying report what they experience to the counseling guidance teacher. Further study can discuss ways to raise victim awareness and how these methods affect victims of bullying and cyberbullying.

4. CONCLUSION

The results of the study show that bullying still occurs in secondary schools in Yogyakarta with 77.1% of students having experienced bullying. The impact felt by the victim is that it suffers psychological effects, such as sadness, worry, fear, decreased trust, anxiety, frustration, decreased self-confidence, and reluctance to engage socially, counseling guidance teachers have an important role in the victim's prevention and psychological recovery efforts, including counseling services for victims and perpetrators, anti-bullying education, Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT), the KiVa Anti-Bullying Program, and digital literacy training. Strengthening school policies, safe

reporting systems, and support networks is essential to fostering student resilience, enabling them to overcome bullying experiences and thrive academically and socially.

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